

D8.1: Report on the Dissemination and Communication Plan

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<p>ABSTRACT:</p>	<p>Any CSA project is heavily dependent on the quality of dissemination and communication, since both types of activities are essential for spreading information about the progress of the project, the events organized and the main findings and other outcomes. This does not only create visibility for the project's findings but also facilitates the engagement activities foreseen by ROSiE. ROSiE can only be considered a successful project if the envisioned impact is achieved. This, in turn, strongly depends on the extent to which its communications are picked up and implemented by our specific beneficiary groups, as described at the DoA document. The consortium has constructed the following three-stage communication strategy, executed within WP8:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a preparatory stage mainly employing social media to generate attention to the subject and the project's aims and objectives and the construction of a user-friendly website that outlines the project and provide regular updates of the progress of the project • dissemination towards relevant stakeholders at an organisational and individual level for awareness of the upcoming ROSiE outcomes • delivery of the ROSiE Knowledge Hub through the project's website.
<p>Keyword List:</p>	

Consortium:

No.	Role	Name	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	ÖSTERREICHISCHE AGENTUR FÜR WISSENSCHAFTLICHE INTEGRITÄT	OeAWI	Austria
3.	Partner	VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN	ECSA	Germany
4.	Partner	EUREC OFFICE GUG	EUREC	Germany
5.	Partner	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAINVALTUUSKUNNASTA	TSV	Finland
6.	Partner	HAUT CONSEIL DE L'EVALUATION DE LA RECHERCHE ET DE L'ENSEIGNEMENT SUPÉRIEUR	HCERES	France
7.	Partner	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE	France
8.	Partner	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	Greece
9.	Partner	UNIVERSIDADE CATÓLICA PORTUGUESA	UCP	Portugal
10.	Partner	LATVIJAS UNIVERSITĀTE	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	TARTU ÜLIKOOL	UT	Estonia
12.	Partner	UNIVERSITETET I SOROST-NORGE	USN	Norway

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1 Introduction

The central strategy for dissemination has been developed by mapping all stakeholders to be included in the dissemination and communication process. The present report contains details on all types of dissemination and communication activities and on how to ensure the highest possible visibility and engagement. A dedicated website will be the intersection point of all dissemination and communication activities, containing the basic tasks of the project, key findings, deliverables, and social media (Twitter and LinkedIn) presence. The ROSiE Knowledge Hub will be hosted in the project's website. A strategy for disseminating the results to academia is not only foreseen through conferences and academic journal articles, but also through social media and all co-creation activities. Finally, WP8 will establish a strong, continuous and structured interaction with other relevant EU-funded projects. Also, ROSiE will pay special attention to engage with the Embassy of Good Science and establish a project page on the Embassy web-site.

The outcomes of WP8, concerning communication and dissemination actions, will directly influence and be influenced by the work in all the other WPs. WP8 will boost visibility of the project's findings, assist stakeholder engagement in WPs 3 (EXPLORE and ENGAGE: Stakeholder Engagement Practices), 4 (EXPLORE and ENGAGE: Horizontal Coordination), enable co-creation activities, upon request from the WP leaders of WPs 6 (EXPLORE, GUIDE, and EQUIP: The ROSiE Knowledge Hub for Open Science) and 7 (EQUIP: Training materials for promoting responsible practice of Open Science), and promote sustainability for ROSiE Knowledge Hub.

Main objective:

To effectively communicate with all stakeholders who have a stake in the success of ROSiE, proactively engage our target audience in the activities of the project and disseminate ROSiE outcomes as widely as possible.

Sub-objectives:

1. Decide the most appropriate types of stakeholders targeted for communication and dissemination and the most appropriate dissemination tools/channels
2. Apply the central dissemination strategy
3. Launch and sustain ROSiE website and social media channels
4. Design actions for the sustainable impact of ROSiE.

2 Central strategy for dissemination

ROSiE envisages a number of dissemination paths, in order to achieve high visibility of the project findings and development cycles. Based on the communication activities approach of ROSiE, we have broken down the means of communication, the messages and the intended effects.

The ROSiE portal (to be launched at the end of June 2021) has the ambition to act as a nodal point. Besides being a website containing ROSiE results, it will also function as an internet platform that aims to integrate parts of existing portals from EU-funded projects that have the following types of outcomes: Guidance and frameworks, Training materials, Platforms, RE/RI in general, and Citizen Science. Table 1 lists these projects. The relevance of ROSiE to these projects is described by the elements presented by the title of the columns. Specifically, these projects will provide contact points with ROSiE with regard Guidance and frameworks, Training materials, Platforms, Research Ethics and Integrity in general, and Citizen Science. The project could potentially attract ongoing RRI projects by asking their coordinators to participate at any kind of events that are going to be organized, taking into account that RRI seeks institutional change; this can be facilitated by the incorporation of the Knowledge Hub and the training materials to be developed by ROSiE.

Table 1: Projects ROSiE is going to target for dissemination reasons

Guidance and Frameworks	TrainingMaterials	Platform	Others on RE/RI	Citizen Science
PRINTEGER	EnTIRE	ENTIRE	MoRRI	NEWSERA
PRO-RES	ENERI	ENERI	SUPER MoRRI	EU-Citizen Science
SOPs4RI	VIRT2UE	EOSC	RRI Tools	CLARIN-ERIC
EnTIRE	RRI Tools	EOSC-Pillar EOSC-Nordic EOSC-Synergy NI4OS-Europe	RRO Practice	FAIRsFAIR
TRUST	HEIRRI	OpenAIRE-Advance	FOSTER PLUS	-
i-CONSENT	FOSTER PLUS	-	-	-
PRO-Ethics	-	-	-	-

Each stakeholder group has different needs from ROSiE. The ROSiE consortium has analysed their respective stakes/needs and has developed a strategy for dissemination: This strategy has defined the means by which to disseminate and what to disseminate in each stakeholder group. The means of dissemination have been elaborated during NTUA's preparation for the project'sKoMand has taken into account all ROSiE beneficiaries' suggestions that came up during the KoM. This deliverable presents the refined dissemination strategy, covering both traditional and non-traditional (e.g. Social Media) channels of communication.

However, the Dissemination and Communication Plan is flexible and will have to integrate amendments during the course of the project; in this sense ROSIE consortium will continuously interact with all stakeholder groups in order to revise/optimize the Dissemination Strategy during the whole duration of the project.

ROSIE’s approach to dissemination is to maximize impact by involving key stakeholders in the engagement activities, so that they are enabled and motivated to carry on the widespread use of the results in the frame of their own implementation and/or dissemination missions and activities. This is, for instance, the case of reaching out to this enlarged group of stakeholders, and not only with the end users, which will be a central element in ROSIE’s impact. ROSIE will **target 11 different stakeholder types**, to whom the consortium has already established strong links due to existing collaboration and discussions during the preparation of the proposal. An overview of the target stakeholders, the purpose of dissemination and the specific channels and tools for dissemination are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Dissemination strategy of ROSIE.

Target stakeholders	Target organisations	Purpose of dissemination	Channels of dissemination	Tools of dissemination
Individual researchers Members of RECs and RIOs Research managers	(academic and industrial) Individuals from the networks of HYBRIDA partners LERU , EUA YERUN , GYA EUREC , ENRIO WCRIF , EARMA AIEA , COPE , EoGS	Recruiting in engagement events Promote ROSIE’s results To inform peers about the potential of CS and of SoundQ Lab for their own research	Engagement events	Oral presentations
			Conferences	Oral/poster presentations
			Workshops	Oral/poster presentations
			“Next steps” conference	Oral presentations/expert panels
			Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn
Science educators		Better STEM education	Engagement events	Oral presentations
			“Next steps” conference	Oral presentations/expert panels
RFOs	HERA , EViR Science Europe Belmont Forum	Aid uptake and promote ROSIE’s results Promote Open Science practices at the organizational	Conferences	Oral/poster presentations
			Press releases	e-Articles
			“Next steps” conference	Oral presentations/expert panels
			Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn

		level		
Research Policy makers Legal experts	EC officials, Politicians at European, National and Local level STOA	Aid uptake and promote ROSiE's results Promote leadership in providing clear procedures on the Open Science platform functioning To build capacity in regions where there is a lack of Open Science awareness	Engagement events	Oral presentations
			Press releases	e-Articles
			"Next steps" conference	Oral presentations/expert panels
			Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn
Science journalists		Raise awareness of ROSiE's findings	"Next steps" conference	Oral presentations/expert panels
			Press releases	e-Articles
			Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn
			ROSiE website	Newsfeed, e-Newsletters
Associations of industries	Business Europe Digital Europe Eurochambre	Promote ROSiE's results	Press releases	e-Articles
			"Next steps" conference	Oral presentations/expert panels
			Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn
			ROSiE website	Newsfeed, e-Newsletters
Citizen Science associations Civil society organizations	EUSEA Sense About Science ENNA Civil Society Europe	Recruit in engagement events (1 st stage of engagement process)	Engagement events	Oral presentations
			ROSiE website	Newsfeed, e-Newsletters

		Promote ROSiE's results Cooperate with them to foster further dissemination of the project's findings Multiply the "pressure" towards policy makers for the adoption of Open Science practices	Social media	Facebook, Twitter
			"Next steps" conference	Oral presentations/expert panels
General public	Media audiences Science audiences Bloggers Active social media users	Raise awareness on ROSiE's findings and on OS at large	ROSiE website	Newsfeed, e-Newsletters
			Social media	Facebook, Twitter
			Public outreach events	Talks in Science Communication and Researcher's Night events

In addition to the specific dissemination channels used by each of its partners, the dissemination scheme of ROSiE relies on dedicated European networks, which encourage and coordinate national and Europe-wide initiatives in RE (EUREC), RI (ENRIO), citizen science (ECSA) and OS (CoNOSC). Depending on their current legal status but with no impact on their actual involvement, these networks are members (EUREC, ECSA, and CoNOSC) or supporters (ENRIO) of the consortium. The combination of these networks is especially well suited both to properly inform the aggregation phase (to map and analyze the interactions between ethics, integrity and OS), and to disseminate the outputs of ROSiE in all national research communities in Europe. The thematic complementarity of these three or four channels and their rooting in the national communities throughout Europe will ensure an optimal dissemination, adapted to each context including vernacular languages.

Table 3: Overview of the European networks where ROSiE members are active participants.

Network	Countries involved	Description	Relationships with ROSiE
EUREC (European Network of Research Ethics)	EU member states: AT, BE, CZ, DE, DK, EE, ES, FI,	Research Ethics Created in 2005, EUREC is	EUREC is a partner of ROSiE (and WP leader)

<p>Committees) http://www.eurecnet.org</p>	<p>FR, GR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK</p> <p>Non-EU MS: CH, NO</p>	<p>a network that brings together already existing national Research Ethics Committees (RECs) associations, networks or comparable initiatives on the European level.</p>	
<p>ENRIO (European Network of Research Integrity Offices) http://www.enrio.eu</p>	<p>EU member states: AT, BE, CZ, DE, DK, EE, ES, FI, FR, GR, HR, IE, IT, LT, LU, NL, PL, PT, SE, SI, SK</p> <p>Non-EU MS: CH, NO, UK</p>	<p>Research Integrity Created in 2007, ENRIO's aims to enhance research integrity within Europe in a world with growing international cooperation by bringing together the national research integrity offices.</p>	<p>ENRIO is a supporter of ROSiE (letter of support annexed).</p> <p>Four partners of ROSiE are national nodes of ENRIO: OeAWI (Austria), Hcéres (via OFIS; France), UCP (via FCT; Portugal) and NTUA (via EARTHnet; Greece); TSV hosts the Finnish node and (as of 2020) the chair of ENRIO.</p>
<p>ECSA (European Citizen Science Association) https://ecsa.citizen-science.net</p>	<p>ECSA has 200+ individual and organizational members from >28 countries across the EU and beyond.</p> <p>ECSA is also a member of the Citizen Science Global Partnership</p>	<p>Citizen Science Created in 2013, ECSA is the reference network of Citizen Science (CS) initiatives, to encourage the growth of the CS movement in Europe in order to enhance involvement of the public in scientific processes. One objective is to develop principles for good practice in CS.</p>	<p>ECSA is a partner of ROSiE (and WP leader)</p>
<p>CoNOSC Council for National Open Science Coordination https://conosc.org/</p>	<p>EU member states: FI, FR, NL</p> <p>Other: primarily European Research Area and Innovation Committee</p>	<p>Open Science Created in Oct. 2019, CoNOSC helps countries to create, update and coordinate their national open science policies.</p>	<p>CoNOSC is a supporter of ROSiE</p> <p>TSV, a partner of the ROSiE consortium, is a founding member of CoNOSC and current chair (as of April 2020).</p>

3 What will be disseminated?

The objectives of this WP set specific targets on what will be disseminated. Specifically:

- Project events for communication reasons (before and after the events)
- Project events for engagement reasons (before the events)
- Project documents
- Project progress
- Regular updates on the projects
- Project findings
- Participation in conferences, workshops of other projects
- Major events in Research Integrity (e.g. World Conferences on Research Integrity, Congress of Research Integrity practice (organized by ENRIO), Final reports of other projects on Research Integrity)

4 How it will be disseminated?

The means of dissemination have been chosen from the beginning of the project. The amount, detail and periodicity/rate of information transfer have been decided according to the target audience. The means of dissemination are conventional and non-conventional and the aim is to raise the visibility of the ROSiE results. Table 4 summarizes the means of communication of ROSiE.

Through targeted and easily accessible communication activities, ROSiE will ensure that interested individuals and organizations from different fields are aware of ROSiE’s progress and findings. WP8 will plan and oversee the application of the Plan for Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation of the project’s results.

In addition to the dissemination strategy, ROSiE partners will undertake communication activities at major milestones in the project. Communication activities to promote ROSiE will be an important aspect of this Coordination and Support Action, in order to increase visibility of the project, gain awareness of the RRI practices and reach a wide range of stakeholders. As part of WP8 the consortium will ensure timely and clear communication of project results to all relevant stakeholder groups.

Table 4: Overview of the communication channels of ROSiE.

<p>Branding: NTUA will develop a brand identity for the ROSiE website, deliverable, presentation and poster templates, based on the provisional logo included at the header of the proposal document. ROSiE brand identity will consist of a logo, color set and choice of typography to be utilized in all types of communication activities.</p>	
<p>Website: A ROSiE website will be launched to provide up to date information on the project, partners, progress, goals and events. The website will contain an intranet private part for internal use for consortium beneficiaries. The open part will be for external use and will contain information for all relevant stakeholders, including the general public, on the progress of the project.</p>	
<p>Social media: Social media are currently instrumental in reaching the general public and relevant stakeholders. ROSiE will utilize LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook to communicate ROSiE’s progress.</p>	
<p>Conferences: ROSiE consortium members will participate in conferences and interact with experts in the field of RE, RI, OS, citizen science and exchange experiences with relevant stakeholders.</p>	
<p>Workshops/networking: ROSiE participants will actively participate in other relevant EU funded project workshops and SwafS cluster workshops organized by the EC.</p>	

<p>Public outreach events: ROSiE partners will participate in open public events, like open lectures in science museums, participations in Researcher’s Night events and in Science Communication events (e.g. Pint of Science).</p>	
<p>ROSiE final conference: To disseminate the project results to key stakeholders and for raising awareness of the potentials and need of responsible open science, we will organize a final project conference.</p>	
<p>Press releases: Press releases, targeting papers with national circulation (e.g., in the countries of ROSiE’s partners, i.e., Norway, France, Austria, Greece, Finland, Portugal, Latvia, Estonia, and Germany) written in the partners’ national languages will boost project’s communication of the latest findings on a National scale.</p>	
<p>Printed material: Dissemination materials such as newsletters and brochures will be produced to inform all relevant stakeholders. Project progress and relevant updates from outside ROSiE will be presented.</p>	
<p>Scientific publications: Publications in leading research ethics journals and publications (e.g., Research Ethics, Ethics and Education, Science and Engineering Ethics, Teaching Ethics, Journal of Law, Medicine and Ethics etc.). Compliant with PlanS, Open Access supports will be preferred and among them, Diamond Open Access; in any circumstance, public repositories will be used to provide Green Open Access.</p>	

Although ROSiE partners’ respective backgrounds and experiences differ, they all have extensive experience in online and offline communication and will use this to communicate with the ROSiE stakeholders. The pre-existence of communication accounts (organizational and individual) and established networks will provide smooth and wide-reaching announcements for the project’s outputs. ROSiE members have already made a plan to specify the communication channels presented in Tables 2 and 4 presents a list of existing regular events from which we will apply the abovementioned communication channels, as well as the respective **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** that the consortium targets in order to consider that the communication activities were successful (Table 5).

Table 5: Key Performance Indicators, and their proposed targets, for ROSiE’s communication activities.

Channel	Tool	Indicator	M12	M24	M36
Website	Newsfeed	Number	15	30	60
	e-newsletters	Number	2	4	6
	Visitors	Number	250	700	2500

Social media	Twitter	followers/tweets	100/10	300/20	1000/50
		retweets/likes	100/50	300/200	500/500
	Facebook	friends/likes	40/80	200/400	500/1000
	LinkedIn	followers/posts	40/20	100/40	200/80
Conferences	Oral/poster presentations	Number	4	8	12
Workshops	Participation	Number	5	10	15
Public events	Researcher's nights	ROSIE booth	1	2	3
ROSIE conference	Presentations, workshops	Nb of participants	Not applied	Not applied	200
Press release	Newspapers	Nb of articles	1	2	4
	e-Magazines	Nb of articles	1	2	4
Printed material	Brochures or leaflets	Nb distributed to stakeholders	200	500	1000
Scientific publications	Peer reviewed papers	Number published	-	2	4
	Science communication events	Nb oral presentations	2	4	6

5 ROSiE logo

The ROSiE logo reflects the main concept that is “**Connecting stakeholders and lay people through dialogue**” (Figure 1). The two basic variations of the ROSiE logo are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1: The concept of the ROSiE logo – two overlapping speech bubbles.

Figure 2: The ROSiE logo – the two basic variations.

This overlapping speech bubbles logo represents the importance ROSiE gives to all types of foreseen engagement processes. Other variations of the logo are depicted below, in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Variations of the ROSiE logo.

6 ROSiE website

ROSiE’s website comprises a classic web page that contains detailed information on the project and its backgrounds, its partners and associated stakeholders, on who funds it, and what its main aims and objectives are. In addition, it renders transparent the respective progress and main stages of ROSiE and provides access to research reports, publications, proceedings, and policy briefs (as far as they can be made available through open access). These detailed background materials will be accompanied by brief abstracts that summarize their relevance and main points for interested audiences.

The ROSiE website’s main structure is currently being designed by NTUA. Its main aesthetic elements are presented below. Since the project has just begun, the structure upon its launch will contain basic elements of information, in order to avoid empty spaces and at the same time attract attention by giving clear and quick information about the project. Before the launch of the website NTUA will circulate the mock ups to all beneficiaries in order to receive feedback and apply all necessary tweaks in the design. During the preparation of this deliverable NTUA designed the main branding elements that were based on the design of the logo that is considered the core branding element of ROSiE dissemination and communication activities. The main design elements are presented in figure 4; they are the color palette, the shapes and the customised icons that are going to compose ROSiE's website. These elements are going to be applied in all kinds of dissemination materials to be produced during ROSiE.

Figure 4: Main design elements of ROSiE website Variations of the ROSiE logo.

Figure 5 presents a mock up of the combination of design elements, while Figure 6 presents 4 combinations of background photos and variations of the project's logo.

Figure 5: Combination of the primary (left) and secondary (right) color palettes and ROSiE branded shapes.

Figure 6: Combinations of background photos and variations of ROSiE logo shape.

7 ROSiE social media presence

Our dissemination through social media networks (LinkedIn and Twitter) will focus on providing pointed, succinct and highly accessible findings. The dissemination will link to the background material provided on the web page whenever this is appropriate, to allow interested audiences to access additional information. Thereby, the active social media strategy also serves to advertise and popularize the project’s web page. Both the web page and social media activities will make users aware of the project’s mailing list and upcoming events of interest to different stakeholder groups.

Figure 7: Setting of ROSiE’s social media presence in LinkedIn and Twitter

Figure 7 presents the front pages of the ROSiE LinkedIn and Twitter accounts. The frequency of dissemination releases through the Social media channels of SOPs4RI are as follows:

Twitter: 3 times per week relevant tweets/retweeting

LinkedIn: Twice a month.

It is characteristic that the first tweet from ROSiE's account was made during the project's kick off meeting, i.e. 15 April 2021. By the time this deliverable is finalised, i.e. 27 April 2022, the ROSiE account already has 90 followers.

8 Deviations from DoA

No deviations from DoA.

